

New Approaches to Hermeneutical Injustice and Their Applications in Mental Health

Symposium organised as part of XI Congress of the Spanish Society for Analytic Philosophy (SEFA), October 1-3, Seville, Spain.

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Esta publicación es parte de los proyectos de I+D+i:

- Conceptual Engineering and Communicative Disruptions: between Semantics and Pragmatics, PID2024-157224NB-I00 financiado/a por MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ FEDER, UE
- Neurodiversity and madness: toward a non-Ideal philosophy of mind PID2024-155717NB-I00 financiado/a por MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/ FEDER, UE
- Juan de la Cierva research grant (JDC2023-052608-I), funded by MCIU/ AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the FSE+

Thematic areas: Philosophy of Language, Philosophy of Mind, Social and Political Philosophy

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Since Miranda Fricker's (2007) seminal introduction of the concept of *hermeneutical injustice*—the harm done to epistemic agents from oppressed groups when they are systematically excluded from shaping the collective conceptual resources needed to make sense of their social experiences—various authors have revisited and expanded upon it. A crucial development is that, while Fricker focused on hermeneutical injustices arising from *conceptual lacunas*, others have focused on the failure to apply relevant *known* concepts (Simion, 2019) due to different reasons, including the *willful hermeneutical ignorance* of available alternative conceptual resources (Pohlhaus, 2012), which underpins *contributory injustices* (Dotson, 2012); the collective refusal to uptake the hermeneutical tools available in a community (Mason, 2011); or the victim's use of a defective or *impostor concept* that prevents them from understanding their experience accurately (Deans, 2024; Falbo, 2022; Picazo Jaque & Delgado, 2024). Relatedly, Bastian (2024) has recently argued that *conceptual injustices* may also occur when agents are wrongfully excluded from (or included in) the application of a concept.

In the philosophy of psychiatry, discussions about epistemic injustice—and hermeneutical injustice in particular—have gained traction in recent years (Drożdżowicz, 2021; Kidd et al., 2025; Scrutton, 2017). This interest is strongly linked to longstanding criticisms of both dominant medical and anti-medical conceptual frameworks in mental health. Despite their opposition, both have been instrumental in downplaying the perspectives and conceptual resources deployed by those on the receiving end of mental health care—i.e., psychiatric users, survivors, patients; the mentally ill or disabled, the mad or cognitively divergent—to challenge both the default pathologizing and the default normalizing of their conditions (Ballesteros, 2025; Chapman & Carel, 2022; Fernández-Castro & Núñez de Prado-Gordillo, forthcoming; Legault et al., 2024).

This symposium focuses on new developments in the conceptualization of hermeneutical and related injustices, exploring their application to mental health issues. The first contribution critically addresses two theoretical conceptions in mental health: the usual conception of objectivity as standardization and the classical realist conception of the mental. Both, it argues, promote epistemic injustice by reducing patients to passive recipients rather than active

participants in the intersubjective negotiation of their mental makeup. The second contribution focuses on the diagnostic category of Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD), arguing that while it may not be inherently flawed, its misuse can obscure individuals' experiences, potentially making it an impostor concept. Drawing on neurodiversity and neuroqueer feminist perspectives, the contribution advocates for a revised concept of BPD that includes patients' voices and resists sexism and ableism, thereby promoting a more epistemically and morally adequate framework. The third contribution proposes an expanded account of *affective hermeneutical injustice*, arguing that some hermeneutical resources not only restrict how people understand and communicate emotions but also actively shape which emotions are experienced. Specifically, it analyzes the case of therapy-speak—everyday misuse of psychological terms—as a source of affective harm. Finally, in line with the previous proposals, the fourth contribution addresses how hermeneutical injustices in mental health contexts—particularly, those involving impostor concepts—can erode agents' identity and agency, with pernicious mental health consequences. Against the thesis that demarcating impostor from adequate concepts hinges on the possibility to draw clear-cut divisions between self and illness, the authors take hermeneutical adequacy to hinge on a concept's beneficial effects for the individual's agential and emotional self-regulatory abilities.

References

- Ballesteros, V. (2025). Objectivity, standardization, and epistemic injustice in psychiatry. *Synthese*, 205(4), 172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-025-05016-4>
- Bastian, L. (2024). Conceptual Injustice. *The Journal of Ethics*, 28(2), 263-286.
- Chapman, R., & Carel, H. (2022). Neurodiversity, epistemic injustice, and the good human life. *Journal of Social Philosophy*, josp.12456. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josp.12456>.
- Deans, D. (2024). Hermeneutical Injustice Through Defective Concept Possession. *Topoi*, 43(5), 1379-1387.
- Dotson, K. (2012). A Cautionary Tale: On Limiting Epistemic Oppression. *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies*, 33(1), 24-47. <https://doi.org/10.5250/fronjwomestud.33.1.0024>
- Drożdżowicz, A. (2021). Epistemic injustice in psychiatric practice: Epistemic duties and the phenomenological approach. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, medethics-2020-106679. <https://doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2020-106679>
- Falbo, A. (2022). Hermeneutical Injustice: Distortion and Conceptual Aptness. *Hypatia*, 37(2), 343-363.
- Fernández-Castro, V., & Núñez de Prado-Gordillo, M. (forthcoming). Neurodiversidad o la Dimensión Política de Lo Mental. In Agata J. Bak (ed.), *Salud: Entre hechos y valores*. Editorial Universidad de Granada.
- Fricke, M. (2007). *Epistemic injustice: Power and the ethics of knowing*. Oxford University Press.
- Kidd, I. J., Spencer, L., & Carel, H. (2025). Epistemic injustice in psychiatric research and practice. *Philosophical Psychology*, 38(2), 503-531.
- Legault, M., Catala, A., & Poirier, P. (2024). Breaking the stigma around autism: Moving away from neuronormativity using epistemic justice and 4E cognition. *Synthese*, 204(3), 84.

- Mason, R. (2011). Two Kinds of Unknowing. *Hypatia*, 26(2), 294-307.
- Picazo Jaque, C., & Delgado, L. (2024). Impostor concepts and hermeneutical injustice. *Actas Del XI Congreso de La Sociedad de Lógica, Metodología y Filosofía de La Ciencia En España: Oviedo, 16-19-07-2024*, pp. 298-299.
- Pohlhaus, G. (2012). Relational Knowing and Epistemic Injustice: Toward a Theory of Willful Hermeneutical Ignorance. *Hypatia*, 27(4), 715-735.
- Scrutton, A. P. (2017). Epistemic Injustice and Mental Illness. In *The Routledge Handbook of Epistemic Injustice*. Routledge.

Concepciones teóricas como factores estructurales de promoción de la injusticia epistémica en psiquiatría

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Desde la publicación de la obra seminal de Miranda Fricker (2007) y el subsecuente desarrollo de los estudios sobre injusticia epistémica, la clínica y la investigación psiquiátricas han constituido uno de los ámbitos de más fértil aplicación de los análisis de las injusticias que afectan a las personas como sujetos de conocimiento (Kidd et al., 2022). Los pacientes psiquiátricos son particularmente vulnerables a diversas formas de injusticia epistémica debido a factores tales como los prejuicios que operan sobre ellos (Crichton et al., 2017; Kurs & Grinshpoon, 2018; Sanati & Kyratsous, 2015; Scrutton, 2017), las dificultades que pueden encontrar para expresarse (Crichton et al., 2017; Drożdżowicz, 2021) y los desequilibrios de poder que existen no solo entre pacientes y profesionales sanitarios, sino también entre pacientes y profesionales responsables de delinear las concepciones teóricas que informan la comprensión y las prácticas en torno a la salud mental (Bueter, 2019; Drożdżowicz, 2021; Gosselin, 2019; Hassall, 2020; Kurs & Grinshpoon, 2018; Scrutton, 2017).

Todos estos factores pueden contribuir tanto a injusticias testimoniales como hermenéuticas. Los reportes en primera persona de los pacientes pueden ser recibidos con menos crédito del que merecen debido a los prejuicios sobre las personas con trastornos mentales, como por ejemplo que son inestables emocionalmente y que están dominadas por sus enfermedades (Crichton et al., 2017); que son irracionales e incomprensibles (Sanati & Kyratsous, 2015); o que son peligrosas, incoherentes e ilógicas (Kurs & Grinshpoon, 2018). El hecho de que los pacientes usualmente hayan de emplear conceptos y categorías propios de los profesionales de la salud mental puede opacar ciertos aspectos de su experiencia, o dificultar la articulación en sus propios términos (Bueter, 2019; Drożdżowicz, 2021; Gosselin, 2019; Hassall, 2020; Knox, 2022; Miller Tate, 2019; Ritunnano, 2022; Scrutton, 2017).

Además de identificar nuevas formas de injusticia epistémica, la literatura reciente ha apuntado hacia diferentes aspectos teóricos que podrían promover las injusticias epistémicas hacia los pacientes, tanto en medicina general como en psiquiatría. La concepción dominante de los trastornos mentales —el modelo biomédico— ha atraído la atención de los investigadores debido a la rigidez de sus bases conceptuales y sus explicaciones centradas en la biología (Bueter, 2019; Crichton et al., 2017; Gosselin, 2019; Hassall, 2020; Kidd et al., 2022; Knox, 2022; Miller Tate, 2019; Ritunnano, 2022; Scrutton, 2017). Una profunda reforma de nuestras concepciones fundamentales sobre la salud ha sido propuesta como un requisito para la justicia epistémica para las personas enfermas, y “las concepciones naturalistas de la salud” han sido identificadas como “epistémicamente injustas en tanto que promueven y requieren el ejercicio de comportamientos epistémicamente injustos” (Kidd & Carel, 2018, p. 226). En este sentido, se ha argumentado que “lo que es epistémicamente injusto puede que sea no solo los agentes, las comunidades y las instituciones, sino las concepciones teóricas de la salud que estructuran nuestras respuestas a la enfermedad y a los trastornos mentales” (Kidd et al., 2022, p. 7).

Nuestra contribución a este simposio se enmarca en esta última línea abierta en los estudios de injusticia epistémica, analizando cómo las concepciones teóricas en torno a la salud mental pueden funcionar como factores estructurales promotores de prácticas epistémicamente injustas en psiquiatría. Particularmente, analizaremos dos concepciones teóricas que, a nuestro juicio, parecen subyacer a diferentes formas de injusticia epistémica en el ámbito psiquiátrico: la concepción de la objetividad como estandarización y la concepción realista clásica de lo mental.

En primer lugar, argumentaremos que el alto valor que se atribuye a la objetividad en psiquiatría, unido a su concepción en términos de conocimiento estandarizado, puede llevar a prácticas epistémicamente injustas en tanto que promueve el trato a los pacientes como meros informantes o, peor, como fuentes de información. De este modo, su agencia epistémica queda mermada; lo cual se cifraría, por ejemplo, en las dificultades que encuentran para poner en juego determinadas interpretaciones de su experiencia o para abordar los aspectos que ellos mismos consideran son los más relevantes. Argumentamos también que el alto valor de la objetividad y su articulación en términos de conocimiento estandarizado forman parte de los propios fundamentos teóricos de la disciplina: debido a que el diagnóstico psiquiátrico se basa fundamentalmente en los reportes de los pacientes, la psiquiatría ha tenido que ingeniar maneras para objetivar los síntomas y trastornos mentales. Según nuestro análisis, pues, la injusticia epistémica a menudo no aparece por desacreditar los reportes, sino debido a las modificaciones que éstos han de sufrir para poder encajar con los conceptos y categorías estandarizados propios de la psiquiatría.

En segundo lugar, recuperamos una idea presente en la obra de Fricker que, hasta donde nos consta, no ha sido explícitamente abordada por la literatura: la estabilización social de los estados intencionales, conforme Fricker la toma del octavo capítulo del *Truth and Truthfulness* de Bernard Williams. Allí, Williams (2002) aboga por la introducción de la deliberación intersubjetiva como parámetro en la determinación de los estados intencionales individuales (estados como anhelos, creencias y deseos), cuyo perfil previo a dicha interacción con otras

personas es mucho menos definido de lo que tendemos a pensar. En su exploración de los daños derivados de la injusticia epistémica testimonial, Fricker (2007, pp. 51-55) adopta esta concepción de lo mental de Williams para mostrar cuán profundos pueden ser éstos, al impedir o dificultar al sujeto la plena participación en esa deliberación intersubjetiva necesaria para la estabilización de la mente y la formación de la identidad. A partir de aquí, nosotros argumentamos que, debido a las peculiaridades de la práctica psiquiátrica, la necesidad de considerar los procesos de estabilización de lo mental se torna acuciante, hasta el punto de que, no hacerlo –como suele ser el caso en psiquiatría, donde suelen operar presupuestos metafísicos de corte realista clásico acerca de lo mental– puede funcionar como otro factor estructural que promueva la injusticia epistémica. En este caso, la asunción de presupuestos realistas sobre lo mental puede abonar las desigualdades epistémicas entre terapeutas como expertos en la descripción e interpretación de los estados mentales de los pacientes y éstos últimos como subsidiarios epistémicos, opacando el impacto que tiene el propio encuentro terapéutico y los conceptos y categorías psiquiátricos en la constitución de los síntomas mentales de los pacientes.

Referencias

- Bueter, A. (2019). Epistemic Injustice and Psychiatric Classification. *Philosophy of Science*, 86(5), 1064–1074.
- Crichton, P., Carel, H., & Kidd, I. J. (2017). Epistemic injustice in psychiatry. *BJPsych Bulletin*, 41(2), 65–70.
- Drożdżowicz, A. (2021). Epistemic injustice in psychiatric practice: Epistemic duties and the phenomenological approach. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 47(12), e69–e69.
- Fricker, M. (2007). *Epistemic injustice: Power and the ethics of knowing*. Oxford University Press.
- Gosselin, A. (2019). “Clinician Knows Best”? Injustices in the Medicalization of Mental Illness. *Feminist Philosophy Quarterly*, 5(2).
- Hassall, R. (2020). The impact of a psychiatric diagnosis on the self-narrative of the recipient. *History & Philosophy of Psychology*, 21(1), 4–10.
- Kidd, I. J., & Carel, H. (2018). Healthcare Practice, Epistemic Injustice, and Naturalism. *Royal Institute of Philosophy Supplement*, 84, 211–233.
- Kidd, I. J., Spencer, L., & Carel, H. (2022). Epistemic injustice in psychiatric research and practice. *Philosophical Psychology*, 1–29.
- Knox, B. (2022). Exclusion of the Psychopathologized and Hermeneutical Ignorance Threaten Objectivity. *Philosophy, Psychiatry, & Psychology*, 29(4), 253–266.
- Kurs, R., & Grinshpoon, A. (2018). Vulnerability of Individuals With Mental Disorders to Epistemic Injustice in Both Clinical and Social Domains. *Ethics & Behavior*, 28(4), 336–346.
- Miller Tate, A. J. (2019). Contributory injustice in psychiatry. *Journal of Medical Ethics*, 45(2), 97–100.
- Ritunano, R. (2022). Overcoming Hermeneutical Injustice in Mental Health: A Role for Critical Phenomenology. *Journal of the British Society for Phenomenology*, 53(3), 243–260.

- Sanati, A., & Kyratsous, M. (2015). Epistemic injustice in assessment of delusions. *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*, 21(3), 479–485.
- Scrutton, A. P. (2017). Epistemic Injustice and Mental Illness. In I. J. Kidd, J. Medina, & G. Pohlhaus (Eds.), *The Routledge handbook of epistemic injustice* (pp. 347–355). Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.

Borderline Personality Disorder and Hermeneutical Injustice

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In this paper, we explore the relation between the diagnostic category of Borderline Personality Disorder (BPD) and hermeneutical injustice. Taking on board some feminist criticisms to this diagnostic category, we first note that BPD would by these criticisms' lights be considered an 'impostor concept', which use would generate or sustain hermeneutical injustice. However, our modest claim in this paper is that the idea of impostor concepts developed in Delgado and Picazo (ms) can be applied here as a warning: there are also impostor *uses* of otherwise adequate concepts. Perhaps BPD is fairly adequate, but impostor uses of this label can engender or perpetuate hermeneutical injustice just as well. We also argue that the alternative viewpoints of neurodiversity and neuroqueer feminism open the door to a revision of this concept that would remedy the hermeneutical injustice.

Hermeneutical injustice occurs when one's understanding of an experience is obscured due to hermeneutical marginalization. An experience can be obscured because of a conceptual lacuna (Fricker's original view), or because of the distorting effect of some other concept. Delgado and Picazo (ms) argue that sometimes an experience is in fact obscured by a distorting concept that, importantly, *seems* to illuminate. These are *impostor concepts*: authoritative but delusive concepts that falsely describe some experience, but can provide the subject with an *illusion of intelligibility* that blocks the search for better hermeneutical tools. One example of this in the field of psychiatry is the concept of hysteria.

Currently, BPD has been subjected to extensive criticism from feminist studies. According to certain feminist critiques (Shaw & Proctor, 2005), BPD is regarded as a gender-based diagnosis that pathologizes women who do not conform to social expectations. The fact that characterizing symptoms of BPD (inappropriate anger, impulsivity and potentially self-damaging behaviour, as exemplified by sexual promiscuity) are gender-based calls into question whether these symptoms should constitute a defensible nosological category (Dorfman & Reynolds, 2023). If these criticisms are correct, the diagnosis of BPD could be understood as an impostor concept, and it would be best to remove it.

Against this position, it has been argued (Lester 2013) that removing the concept may potentially invalidate the physical and mental suffering that this condition can entail. Eliminating the concept may thus involve an undue depathologization. Using Fricker's terminology, we could perhaps say that removing the concept would create a situation of a hermeneutical lacuna, where some people would be unable to conceptualize their experiences and suffering. Some patients find this psychiatric label useful in making sense of their experiences, and consider BPD a more accurate diagnosis than other alternatives such as bipolar disorder or post-traumatic stress disorder (Aftab, 2024). Therefore, if BPD can still be useful in some ways, perhaps the concept needs to be repaired rather than discarded, in particular to prevent the possible impostor uses that this concept may invite.

Clearly, the concept should be repaired so that it is both epistemically and morally adequate, i.e., so that it fulfills the hermeneutical role of making experiences intelligible in an epistemically accurate way, and doesn't perpetuate sexist and ableist biases. Furthermore, this reparation should not arise in a situation of hermeneutical marginalization of the target individuals if it is to overcome hermeneutical injustice.

Here we claim that the neurodiversity (Chapman, 2023) and neuroqueer feminist (Johnson, 2021) paradigms might be on the right track from the perspective of hermeneutical justice. These paradigms propose a broader framework for re-evaluating the BPD condition which crucially incorporates the patients' perspective and experiences. We think this is precisely a way to overcome hermeneutical marginalization. This framework could lead to a reparation of the concept, once free from gender-bias and stigma, and would therefore contribute to remedy hermeneutical injustice.

References

- Aftab, A. (2024) Borderline Personality and Self-Understanding of Psychopathology: Reflections on BPD and hermeneutical justice. *Psychiatry at the Margins*, June 16th.
- Delgado, L. and Picazo, C. (ms) Blocking Meaning Creation: Impostor Concepts and Hermeneutical Injustice.
- Dorfman, N., & Reynolds, J. M. (2023). The New Hysteria: Borderline Personality Disorder and Epistemic Injustice. *IJFAB: International Journal of Feminist Approaches to Bioethics*, 16(2), 162-181.
- Falbo, A. (2022). Hermeneutical Injustice: Distortion and Conceptual Aptness. *Hypatia* 37 (2): 343-363.
- Fricker, M. (2007). *Epistemic Injustice: Power and the Ethics of Knowing*. Oxford University Press.
- Jenkins, K. (2017). Rape Myths and Domestic Abuse Myths as Hermeneutical Injustices. *Journal of Applied Philosophy* 34 (2):191-205.
- Johnson, M. L. (2021). Neuroqueer feminism: turning with tenderness toward borderline personality disorder. *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, 46(3), 635-662.

Lester, R. J. (2013). Lessons from the borderline: Anthropology, psychiatry, and the risks of being human. *Feminism & Psychology*, 23(1), 70-77.

Shaw, C., & Proctor, G. (2005). I. Women at the margins: A critique of the diagnosis of borderline personality disorder. *Feminism & Psychology*, 15(4), 483-490.

The Twofold Nature of Affective Hermeneutical Injustice

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The literature on affective injustice has emphasized how social conditions, including norms, practices, and relationships, can exert oppression on people's affective states (Stockdale, 2023). One of the forms of affective injustice that has been analyzed is affective hermeneutical injustice –also known as affect-related hermeneutical injustice, which occurs when marginalized groups are unfairly constrained in their capacity to understand and share affective experiences because they lack access to the relevant hermeneutical resources (Gallegos, 2021). In this paper, we argue that another form of this type of injustice has been overlooked: certain hermeneutical resources can harm people's affective lives not only by hindering their capacity to understand and share their emotions, but also by *generating* the emotions that are experienced in the first place. In this paper, we propose an expanded account of affective hermeneutical injustice, which characterizes the active character of concepts in shaping our affective life as twofold: hermeneutical resources determine not only what can be expressed and understood, but also what can be felt. To support this claim, we focus on the case of therapy-speak.

Therapy-speak is a linguistic practice that involves the imprecise and superficial use of psychotherapy-related terms in everyday communication, often by members of wealthier social classes (Isern-Mas & Almagro, n.d.; Almagro & Isern, n.d.; Waldman, 2021). For instance, in therapy-speak the word “trauma” is used to refer to a mildly uncomfortable situation, and the word “OCD” to describe a tidy person (e.g., Medaris, 2024). The harms of therapy-speak can be analyzed from the frameworks of epistemic and affective injustice (Isern-Mas & Almagro, n.d.; Spencer & Carel, 2021). In particular, therapy-speak can be argued to cause affect-related hermeneutical injustice.

The original account of affective hermeneutical injustice has been proposed by Gallegos (2021), inspired by Fricker's (2007) account of hermeneutical injustice. According to Fricker (2007), hermeneutical injustice occurs when the experiences of a group are misunderstood or overlooked due to that group's unequal access to, or marginalization from the development of, the shared hermeneutical resources needed to interpret those experiences. Accordingly, Gallegos (2021) affect-related hermeneutical injustice occurs when marginalized groups are unfairly constrained in their capacity to understand and share *affective* experiences because they lack access to the relevant hermeneutical resources. An example of this form of injustice

might be women's struggle to understand their negative affective experiences after birth because they lack access to the concept of "postpartum depression" (Fricker, 2007), or an asexual person understanding their affective experience as mental health problem rather than legitimate sexual orientation (Santos, 2022).

However, recent developments of the concept of hermeneutical injustice have emphasized other causes of hermeneutical injustice, beyond conceptual gaps or lack of access to the relevant hermeneutical resources (Falbo, 2022; Dotson, 2012; Mason, 2011; Pohlhaus, 2012). For instance, Falbo (2022) argues that hermeneutical injustice does not just emerge from a gap in our conceptual resources, but "from the overabundance of distorting and oppressive concepts that function to crowd out, defeat, or preempt the application of an available and more accurate concept" (p. 344). In these situations, the appropriate conceptual tools might already exist; there are simply other competing concepts that have a growing presence doing the work, maybe because they are supported by epistemically powerful institutions and practices. This has not been sufficiently acknowledged and explored by the available accounts on affective injustice so far, thus we contribute to filling this gap.

Applying these developments on hermeneutical injustice to the affective realm, affective hermeneutical injustice occurs not only because of a gap in our conceptual resources, but also because we have distorted and oppressive concepts that make us misinterpret our affective states. Following this analysis, Lavalée and Gagné-Jullian (2024) have argued that the psychiatrization of everyday emotions imposes the hermeneutic resources of the biomedical model on individuals with mental health struggles, marginalizing alternative ones, and thereby harming their affective life. Similarly, in the case of therapy-speak, an overworked employee may self-attribute affective states of lack of resilience (along with affective states such as lack of willpower, effort capacity, etc.), when in reality what they feel is exhaustion or stress due to overwork. The employer misunderstands their emotional life because they use an inappropriate yet powerful concept which is in conflict with a more appropriate although less powerful one.

The use of therapy-speak not only hinders people's capacity to understand and share their experiences, but it also *shapes* those experiences. In our view, our affective life is not only something that we can discover with more or less accuracy with the aid of appropriate concepts, it's also something that we construe, and when the concepts we have are not appropriate, we can end up constructing a distorting picture of our affections. In consequence, therapy-speak illuminates another, perhaps stronger, form of affective hermeneutical injustice which has been overlooked by standard analyses of hermeneutical injustice: certain hermeneutical resources can cause affective hermeneutical injustice not only by hindering people's capacity to understand and share their emotions, but also by shaping how these emotions are experienced in the first place. Thus, in this work we explore how certain hermeneutical resources shape our affective life and lead us to have affective states that otherwise we would not have, due to contexts of social oppression.

An implication of this for the literature on affective injustice is that two forms of affective hermeneutical injustice can be identified: a weak and a strong one. In the weak one, certain

hermeneutical resources about our affective life lead to a misinterpretation of what is really being felt. In the strong one, certain hermeneutical resources about our affective life lead to feeling affective states that otherwise we would not feel (and that are due to contexts of social injustice). Hermeneutical resources thus serve not only an interpretative function, but also a productive one.

References

- Almagro, M. & Isern-Mas, C. Blunting Concepts: Therapy-Speak and Hermeneutical Injustice.
- Dotson, K. (2012). A cautionary tale: On limiting epistemic oppression. *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies*, 33(1), 24-47. <https://doi.org/10.5250/fronjwomestud.33.1.0024>
- Falbo, A. (2022). Hermeneutical Injustice: Distortion and Conceptual Aptness. *Hypatia*, 37, 343–363.
- Fricke, M. (2007). *Epistemic injustice: Power and the ethics of knowing*. Oxford University Press.
- Gallegos, F. (2021). Affective injustice and fundamental affective goods. *Journal of Social Philosophy*, 53(2), 185-201. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josp.12428>
- Isern-Mas, C. & Almagro, M. Unmasking Therapy-Speak.
- Lavallee, Z., & Gagné-Julien, A. M. (2024). Affective injustice, sanism and psychiatry. *Synthese*, 204(3), 94. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-024-04731-8>
- Mason, R. (2011). Two kinds of unknowing. *Hypatia*, 26(20), 294–307. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.2011.01175.x>
- Medaris, A. (2024, September 1). Seven of the most frequently misused psychological terms. *Monitor on Psychology*, 55(6). <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2024/09/therapy-misspeak>
- Pohlhaus, G., Jr. (2012). Relational knowing and epistemic injustice: Toward a theory of “wilful hermeneutical ignorance”. *Hypatia*, 27(4), 715–735. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1527-2001.2011.01222.x>
- Santos, E. (2022, July 9). "Mis 24 años de vida sin saber que soy asexual siento que me los han robado". *Huffpost*. https://www.huffingtonpost.es/entry/asexualidad_es_62b1999ee4b0cf43c85b8f3d.html
- Spencer, L., & Carel, H. (2021). ‘Isn’t Everyone a Little OCD?’: The Epistemic Harms of Wrongful Depathologization. *Philosophy of Medicine*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5195/pom.2021.19>
- Stockdale, K. (2023). (Why) Do We Need a Theory of Affective Injustice?. *Philosophical Topics*, 51(1), 113-134. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/48776806>
- Waldman, K. (2021, March 26). The Rise of Therapy-Speak. *The New Yorker*. <https://www.newyorker.com/culture/cultural-comment/the-rise-of-therapy-speak>

Speaking One's Mind in Tongues: Hermeneutical Injustice and Agency in Mental Health

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Several philosophers have pointed out that related notions like self-regulation, self-narrative, self-understanding or self-concepts are central to understanding mental health and disorder (De Haan, 2023; Dembić, 2023; Zawidzki, 2024). Given the harm that various forms of epistemic injustice can inflict on self-understanding and agency (Roessler, 2014) alongside the specific epistemic injustices faced by psychiatrized populations (Kidd et al., 2025), it is crucial to examine how hermeneutical injustice may undermine self-interpretative capacities, thereby worsening mental health.

This paper explores how different types of hermeneutical injustice can erode identity via distorting self-concepts and self-narratives, with harmful consequences for individuals' mental health and agency. Contributing to ameliorate such injustices thus requires distinguishing between distorting and epistemically appropriate concepts. Against a restricted epistemological view according to which good concepts are those that allow us to track ready-made, clear-cut boundaries between disorder and self, we argue that such realist commitment is problematic; instead, we defend that lacking such clear distinction is not really a problem for distinguishing potentially damaging concepts from innocuous ones.

Fricker's (2007) original account of hermeneutical injustice explains it in terms of *conceptual lacunas* in collective interpretative resources that impede the articulation of the social experiences of the disenfranchised. By contrast, more recent work focuses on the failure to apply *available* alternative conceptual resources—either due to *willful ignorance* of the alternative conceptual resources developed by disenfranchised groups (Polhaus, 2012; see also Dotson, 2012) or to the imposition of *impostor concepts* that systematically distort an accurate understanding of the target experience (Deans, 2024; Falbo, 2022; Picazo Jaque & Delgado, 2024).

In mental health contexts, many examples of hermeneutical injustice are of the latter kind: they involve situations where the hermeneutical tools available to psychiatrized individuals are *distorted*—whether by stigma, undue patronizing, illness-related stereotypes, or implicit assumptions of medical practice itself. For example, Jackson (2017) notes how attitudes toward depression can include naive denials of the disorder, which trivializes its significance and unfairly questions the individual's ability to gauge the depth of their own experiences; or romanticization, which frames depression as a mark of genius or poetic sensitivity, thereby obscuring its debilitating consequences. These attitudes can be internalized by individuals, resulting in hermeneutical injustices that distort the way they understand their own condition. Similarly, Ritunanno (2022) has argued that psychotic individuals may experience

hermeneutical injustices not only because adequate hermeneutical resources are lacking from collective resources but also because of “negative stereotypes associated with psychotic experiences such as rigid binary assumptions of incomprehensibility, meaninglessness and dysfunction” (p. 248). Finally, the neurodiversity movement (Chapman, 2023) has long questioned the deficit assumptions involved in the typification of psychological conditions like autism or ADHD. From this point of view, the default assumption that divergent cognitive styles are deficient or disordered amounts to hermeneutical injustices insofar as it forces individuals to think of their experiences as being deficient or dysfunctional, blocking alternative neurodiversity-affirming interpretations.

Here, we are interested in cases of hermeneutical injustices where the victim uses a defective or impostor concept instead of a more epistemically appropriate one. Specifically, we argue that these impostor concepts are not merely harmful because they hinder the agents’ self-interpretation resources but also because they undermine their autonomy by distorting their self-knowledge and self-worth (Roessler 2014), thereby posing harmful consequences for their mental health. However, this raises a critical question: How to distinguish impostor concepts from legitimate ones? This is far from trivial in cases like the ones discussed. Take depression. On the one hand, romanticizing depression may obscure individuals’ very real struggles and suffering. On the other, scholars in *Mad Studies* may argue that certain depressive traits can be rightfully reframed as “*dangerous gifts*”—a perspective that highlights potential strengths tied to the condition, with potential therapeutic value (Mitchell-Brody, 2007). Similarly, although neurodiversity activists argue that *default pathologizing* narratives are alienating and reductive, this does not mean that pathologizing narratives are always harmful; in fact, the *default normalization* of divergent conditions may also be detrimental to individuals, preventing them from seeking beneficial interventions or needed resources (Chapman, 2023).

What, then, makes a concept epistemically appropriate? The most apparent answer would be that epistemically appropriate concepts enable us to reliably differentiate mental health conditions from a “core” self. On this view, determining whether concepts are impostors or epistemically appropriate would be a matter of accumulating sufficient empirical evidence about pre-existing boundaries between self and illness. However, this solution faces several problems. First, it presupposes realism regarding mental phenomena and the self-illness divide. As Jeppsson has argued (2022), this perspective faces several problems. First, it is not clear if we can—or even should—treat such boundaries as pre-existing phenomena we *discover*. Second, realism can lead to a problematic suspension of judgment and ameliorative inaction: if we cannot definitively separate self from illness, we arguably shouldn’t take a stance until we know whether a concept is truly an impostor, thereby paralyzing efforts to address perceived injustices.

We argue that distinguishing between impostor and non-impostor concepts by appealing to a concept's ability to track facts implies a rather restrictive view of the epistemic domain. First, a non-impostor concept can be defined as one that places the agent in a better position to exercise their agency given their values, self-esteem, or capacity to reflect on them. Second, we understand that a concept is epistemically more adequate when it puts the agent in a better

position to interpret their own behavior and experience in such a way that their emotional reactions attached to their behavior and experience do not constitute a failure of their own agency.

References

- Bastian, L. (2024). Conceptual Injustice. *The Journal of Ethics*, 28(2), 263-286.
- Chapman, R. (2023). *Empire of normality: Neurodiversity and capitalism*. Pluto Press.
- De Haan, S. (2023). What do my problems say about me? *Philosophical Explorations*, 26(2), 159-164.
- Deans, D. (2024). Hermeneutical Injustice Through Defective Concept Possession. *Topoi*, 43(5), 1379-1387.
- Dembic, S. (2023). Mental disorder: An ability-based view. *Philosophy and the Mind Sciences*, 4.
- Falbo, A. (2022). Hermeneutical Injustice: Distortion and Conceptual Aptness. *Hypatia*, 37(2), 343-363.
- Fricker, M. (2007). *Epistemic injustice: Power and the ethics of knowing*. OUP.
- Jackson, J. (2017). Patronizing Depression: Epistemic Injustice, Stigmatizing Attitudes, and the Need for Empathy. *Journal of Social Philosophy*, 48(3), 359-376.
- Jeppsson, S. M. I. (2022). Solving the self-illness ambiguity: The case for construction over discovery. *Philosophical Explorations*, 25(3), 294-313.
- Kidd, I. J., Spencer, L., & Carel, H. (2025). Epistemic injustice in psychiatric research and practice. *Philosophical Psychology*, 38(2), 503-531.
- Mason, R. (2011). Two Kinds of Unknowing. *Hypatia*, 26(2), 294-307.
- Mitchell-Brody, M. (2007). The Icarus Project: Dangerous Gifts, Iridescent Visions and Mad Community. *The Icarus Project Archive*.
- Picazo Jaque, C., & Delgado, L. (2024). Impostor concepts and hermeneutical injustice. *Actas Del XI Congreso de La Sociedad de Lógica, Metodología y Filosofía de La Ciencia En España: Oviedo, 16-19-07-2024*, pp. 298-299.
- Pohlhaus, G. (2012). Relational Knowing and Epistemic Injustice: Toward a Theory of Willful Hermeneutical Ignorance. *Hypatia*, 27(4), 715-735.
- Ritunnano, R. (2022). Overcoming Hermeneutical Injustice in Mental Health: A Role for Critical Phenomenology. *Journal of the British Society for Phenomenology*, 53(3), 243-260.
- Roessler, B. (2014). Autonomy, Self-Knowledge, and Oppression. En *Personal Autonomy and Social Oppression*. Routledge.
- Tekin, Ş. (2011). Self-concept through the diagnostic looking glass: Narratives and mental disorder. *Philosophical Psychology*, 24(3), 357-380.
- Zawidzki, T. W. (2024). Skilled metacognitive self-regulation toward interpretive norms: A non-relativist basis for the social constitution of mental health and illness. *Synthese*, 204(3), 109.